

Studies on Quinoline and Phenothiazine. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenylurea-s-triazine and 1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-(acetylphenylurea)phenothiazine

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SEVERAL quinoline derivatives are used in medicinal industry. Central nervous system depressant and analgesic activity are shown by the urea derivatives of quinolines¹. Schulemann and Mietzsch² selected 8-aminoquinoline series to prepare antimalarial drugs. Moreover, 8-hydroxyquinoline derivatives are active amoebicides and phenothiazine derivatives have insecticidal³ activity. One of the most important uses of phenothiazine is in the control of mosquitoes for it is toxic to their larve⁴. These derivatives also show anthelmintic activity. The urea derivatives possess antibacterial⁵, hypnotic, anaesthetic and other therapeutic activities. Several workers have investigated *s*-triazine nucleus as potential therapeutic agents and phenoxy ethers of *s*-triazine are well known fungicides⁶.

In order to synthesise some active compounds, we have synthesised 2-morpholine-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenylurea-*s*-triazine (1) and 1,3,7,9-tetrachloro-10-(acetylphenylurea)phenothiazine (2) derivatives.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded with a Backmann IR-5 spectrophotometer equipped with NaCl prism.

Section I :

2-Morpholino-4-6 dichloro-*s*-triazine : Morpholine (4.5 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in acetone was added in well stirred solution of cyanuric chloride (9.5 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in acetone. The mixture was refluxed at 80-90° for 3 h and maintaining the pH at 6-7. It was poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol, 70%, m.p. 185°.

2-Morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine : 2-Morpholino-4,6-dichloro-*s*-triazine (11.8 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in acetone was added in a solution as 8-hydroxyquinoline (8.0 g, 0.05 mol) dissolved in acetone at 35° with stirring. The temperature was raised to 45° and stirred for further 2 h, filtered and crystallised from 95% ethanol, 60%, m.p. 125°.

General method of preparation of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenylurea-*s*-triazine (1) : 2-Morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (18.0 g, 0.05 mol) and various phenyl ureas dissolved in acetone were refluxed at 80-90° for 3 h, maintaining the pH at 7. The mixture was poured on crushed ice, filtered and crystallised from ethanol.

Melting points of the compounds are as follows : R=phenyl, 195°; *o*-tolyl, 185°; *m*-tolyl, 150°; *p*-tolyl, 170°; *o*-nitrophenyl, 135°; *m*-nitrophenyl, 16°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 158°; *o*-chlorophenyl, 140°; *m*-chlorophenyl, 155°; and *p* chlorophenyl, 178°. All the compounds in general gave the following ir bands : 1 480-1 540 (NH stretch), 1 670-1 690 (CO), 1 640-1 740 (CONHCO) and 820-880 cm⁻¹ (C_sN₃ stretch).

Section II :

1,3,7,9 Tetrachlorophenothiazine : Diphenylamine (1.0 mol) and thionyl chloride (1.5 mol) were heated on a water-bath for 1 h. The contents were cooled and poured on crushed ice to yield 1,3,7,9-tetrachlorophenothiazine, which was crystallised from benzene, 81%, m.p. 236°.

1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-(chloroacetyl)phenothiazine : 1,3,7,9-Tetrachlorophenothiazine (41.3 g) in dry benzene (100 ml) and chloroacetyl chloride (18 ml) in dry benzene (100 ml) were refluxed on a water-bath for 2.5 h. Phosphorous pentoxide (5 g) was added as condensing agent and on evaporation of solvent the product was obtained, filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene, m.p. 180°.

General method of preparation of 1,3,7,9-tetrachloro-10-(acetylphenylurea)phenothiazine (2) : 1,3,7,9-Tetrachloro-10-(chloroacetyl)phenothiazine (0.05 mol) and various phenylureas (0.012 mol) were refluxed in thiophene-free benzene for 3-4 h. The products were crystallised from benzene.

Melting points of compounds are as follows : R=Phenyl, 185°; *o*-tolyl, 90°; *m*-tolyl, 120°; *p*-tolyl, 215°; *o*-nitrophenyl, 205°; *m*-nitrophenyl,

150°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 180°; *o*-chlorophenyl 185°; and *p*-chlorophenyl 197°. All the compounds in general gave the following ir bands: 1 480–1 540 (NH stretch), 1 640–1 680 (C=O with aromatic phenyl group) and 820–880 cm⁻¹ (C₃N₃ stretch).

The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) and gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at the concentration of 10 mg ml⁻¹. The same method was adopted for determining antiseptic activity using *Streptococcus ficalis*. The zone of inhibition of both the activities of the test solution was recorded.

Maximum zone of inhibition was obtained for the culture *S. aureus*, in the case of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenoxy-(*p*-chlorophenylurea)-*s*-triazine. In the culture *E. coli*, maximum zone of inhibition was obtained in case of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenoxy-(*o*-chlorophenylurea)-*s*-triazine. Maximum zone of inhibition with culture *S. ficalis* was obtained in case of 2-morpholino-4-(8'-oxyquinolino)-6-phenoxy-(*o*-chlorophenylurea)-*s*-triazine.

For both *S. aureus* and *E. coli*, 1,3,7,9-tetrachloro-10-(acetyl-*o*-nitrophenylurea)phenothiazine exhibited maximum zone of inhibition. In case of *S. ficalis*, 1,3,7,9-tetrachloro-10-(acetyl-*m*-nitrophenylurea)phenothiazine exhibited maximum zone of inhibition.

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Chemical Investigation of *Salvia lanata* Roxb. and *Bignonia anguis Cati*

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IN previous communications¹⁻⁴, we reported the isolation and identification of some di- and tri-terpenes from the whole plant (aerial parts and roots) of *Salvia lanata* Roxb.⁵. We now report

the isolation and characterisation of two more diterpenes from the benzene extract of *S. lanata* and the result of systematic chemical examination of *Bignonia anguis Cati*⁶ (Bignoniaceae) on which no phytochemical work seems to have been reported so far.

The concentrated benzene extract of the defatted whole plant of *S. lanata* was subjected to chromatographic analysis over silica gel, elution being carried out with solvents and solvent mixtures of increasing polarity. The later fraction of benzene eluate furnished a diterpene, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ (*M*⁺ 314), m.p. 165–68°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 210, 248, 330sh and 455 nm; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350, 1 660 and 1 630 cm⁻¹ (*o*-hydroxyparabenzoquinone). On catalytic hydrogenation over Adam's catalyst followed by oxidation by air it formed a compound, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ (*M*⁺ 316), m.p. 178–80°, identical with royleanone (m.m.p., co-ir and co-tlc with authentic specimen⁷) and was characterised as 6-dehydroroyleanone⁷. Further elution of the column with benzene–chloroform (1 : 1) afforded a gummy residue which dissolved in solvent ether, extracted with 5% NaOH solution, acidified with cold dilute HCl and extracted with solvent ether. The concentrated ether extract was chromatographed over silica gel and the benzene eluate yielded a crystalline solid, C₂₀H₂₈O₃ (*M*⁺ 300), m.p. 290–92°; λ_{max} (EtOH) 230 and 280 nm (phenol); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 300 (phenolic OH), 1 670 cm⁻¹ (conjugated ketone) and was characterised as sugiol⁸.

The air-dried powdered whole plant of *B. anguis Cati* was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and methanol. The concentrated petroleum ether extract on chromatographic separation over silica gel gave a white solid, (*M*⁺ 410), m.p. 83–84°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 cm⁻¹ (associated OH) in petroleum ether eluate. The compound has been identified as octacosanol⁹ by usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic sample. The concentrated methanolic extract of the defatted whole plant was chromatographed over silica gel and the elution of the column with ethyl acetate furnished a light yellow solid crystallised from methanol, (*M*⁺ 450), m.p. 215–16°; ν_{max} 3 350 (OH), 1 670 (tetrasubstituted double bond) and 1 695 cm⁻¹ (conjugated C=C). The identity of this compound with tectol¹⁰ has been established by the usual comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic sample of tectol. Further elution of the column with the same solvent afforded another solid, (*M*⁺ 302), m.p. 340°; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 345 (bonded OH) and 1 730 cm⁻¹ (lactone). It was characterised as ellagic acid¹¹ through direct comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir) with the authentic specimen.

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